

8T – Dark Energy as Adiabatic variant and The Development of The Universe

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, a varying (3,1) manifold in its second representation, i.e. universe packets, it is possible to make a prediction regarding the rate of change of dark energy. In the 8T thesis it was assumed not to change, however if the universe packet increases in number and additional manifolds are getting flattened than there could be slight variations. I.e. dark energy could be adiabatic variant.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor, given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is wrapped in an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvature and so flatten each other, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21).

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Now suppose that the universe packet contains a finite number, in equation (1.1) the index of the equation will be set as $n = k$. At later temporal segment, the universe packet has increased in insignificant amount, and additional manifold was created by matrix tensor fluctuations of a pre-existed manifold. The new manifold is dense and has certain amount of curvature that will cause an acceleration due to its being in the manifold packet. Now the universe packet has increased in number $n = k + 1$. If so, so does the rate of the overall acceleration. Assuming $k \rightarrow \infty$ the additional manifold just added is not significant and the rate of change could be regarded as adiabatically varying. Since the number of the universe packet can only increase over time, so does the outward acceleration from areas of extremum curvature on each manifold. So by analyzing according to this viewpoint, there should be a slight increase of the "dark energy" overtime, assuming the universe packet increase in number.

It is also unclear whether there are several universe packets or just a singular universe packet in the multiverse. If there are several, what is their configuration, what is the distance between each universe in the packet. If the number increase overtime, the packet should get denser and denser, and the distance as a result must be smaller and smaller. There could be an upper limit to the distance. Using that framework we can predict that the more universes are in the packet, the flatter the matrix tensor should be. Each manifold is than is getting colder and colder and the bosonic interactions in which it experience gets weaker and weaker according to the principle of least curvature and the primordial coupling constants series. Bosonic fields to be net curvature on the varying Lorentz manifold. Those Bosons are isomorphic to prime numbers or one - $\mathbb{P} \cup (+1)$, and propagating from matter clusters destabilized by the majestic (3), which is the electron, from the second element and above.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.3}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.31}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.32}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.33}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

These bosonic ripples are weaker and weaker as the ratio between net curvature to the total curvature is aspiring zero, $\frac{N_V}{T_V} \rightarrow 0$. That is another way to represent the idea in which curvature is "not allowed", or the flatness of the universe. Each of those bosonic fields from the second and above, are generated by the invariant three in the bracket. Those bosonic fields than are forming a cyclic group, as presented in equation (1.34). that is a proof that they are themselves cycles or spinning curvature vortexes.

$$(3) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(5)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.35)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.36)$$

$$\mathcal{B} = \{N_1 = (+3)\mathcal{M}, N_2 = +(\gamma)\mathcal{M} \dots\} \quad (1.37)$$

As the universes gets flatter, the bosonic net curvature gets weaker and the probability of finding each of those getting smaller and smaller, aspiring zero eventually. We presented the following version of the primorial:

$$N_V = (+3) \rightarrow P(A) \quad (2)$$

$$P(A) < 1$$

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) + \mathcal{M} \right) + P(A) \quad (2.1)$$

$$A \in \mathbb{P};$$

By ignoring the constants and assuming same probability of locating the bosons for each coupling term:

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \quad (3)$$

Let $A \rightarrow \infty$

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \rightarrow 0 \quad (3.1)$$

So overall by analyzing according to all those equations, the universe gets more flat, there could be slight increases in the so called- "dark energy", due to additional manifold getting flattened within the ever growing packet. The interactions gets bigger in size and weaker in magnitude and the probability to detect those interactions gets smaller and smaller, aspiring zero as it than becomes depended upon longer chain of events with probability smaller than one. The 8T is a complete framework, synoptic in two equations, the main equation (1) and the primorial coupling constants equation which has many representations. Those predictions regarding the development of the universe were made only by those two equations.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)